

ANALYTICAL STUDY TO REVIEW OF ARABIC LANGUAGE LEARNING USING INTERNET WEBSITES

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ABSTRACT

Arabic language is one of the most commonly used language in the world. It plays a very important role in educational operations around the world. It contains various parts such as poetry, poem, novel, and stories, as well as linguistic and grammatical rules and movements of letters, which change the word according to the movements accompanying each letter, for example, there are movements of lifting and breaking and annexation and silence. In this paper, we will review the research papers that studied the Arabic language learning websites, using the content analysis to determine strengths, weaknesses, advantages, disadvantages, and limitations. This research paper concluded that there is still a shortage and scarcity in the number of articles and websites on the internet that teach Arabic language. The suggestion is to assign task of development to Arab world instituties and others by increasing their number of websites on the internet and enriching their scientific content to improve it and increase its spread between the learners.

KEYWORDS

Arabic language, learning, teaching, websites.

1. INTRODUCTION

Arabic is one of the Semitic languages (or indeed Afroasiatic) [9] [17]; it is written from right to left. It is the most recent, but some believe it is the closest to the source, in order to keep Arabs in the Arabian Peninsula. The Arabic speakers believe their language is the most important language because Allah himself speaks Arabic in the Quran, which is the latest of Holy Books, and they are very proud of the Arabic language. In [10], the authors discussed various aspects of Arabic language, especially how to employ the technology in learning and teaching Arabic languages.

Arabic language is in fourth place with 315 million people speaking Arabic as it is the first language of 26 countries and all Muslims around the world use Arabic in their prayers. Arabic language spread across the Middle East countries and North African countries. Arabic language is very important because it is the language of the world's second-biggest religion (Islam) [11].

Let's look at the framework of the assessment of websites based on the perspectives according to researchers. In [1], fifteen criteria were proposed to evaluate websites such as purpose, accuracy, and multimedia. In [8], to evaluate a website for English language, learning proposed various factors which include usability which means the spread of websites among audience and it has a good reputation. The speed of browsing the pages and downloading content, ease of use which means how to use websites and are also flexible to navigation. Usefulness of the materials is enough for learners. Integrity and professionalism, which means the website should follow the ethical criteria. In [2], a design has elaborated its interactive learning activities and was forwarded for teachers to enhance their learning and teaching approximations. The main contribution of this

article includes a review of Arabic language learning using websites, study, and highlights some aspects in Arabic language using English language.

Arabic language has various dialects distributed in the Arab countries; those dialects have the same root, which means the same meaning [19]. The most common dialects are standard Arabic, Hejazi Arabic, Hadhrami Arabic, Egyptian Arabic, Levantine Arabic, and others. Standard Arabic is used in education and formal reading and writing.

2. ARABIC LANGUAGE

The Arabic language is one of the most important languages in the world. It is called the language of “Al-dhad”, also it is a wide language that is very rich in meanings and words. In addition, it is an official language in all Arab world countries and some Middle East countries. Moreover, the Muslims need Arabic language to read the holy Quran and read the biography of prophet Mohammed and his instructions, and what to say in their prayers. Arabic language is one of the six official languages of the United Nations. It is one of the most widespread languages in the world. Arabic has twenty-eight letters, and some linguists believe that the letter of “Al- Hamzah” should be added to Arabic letters so that the number of letters will be 29 letters. In addition, Arabic language is written from right to left and from top to bottom. Arabic language is one of the Semitic languages, and the origin of the oldest Arabic texts found in the third century AD, which are texts of poetry have a very nice style. The origin of Arabic language dates back to the Hijaz in the Arabian Peninsula, and it developed over time due to several factors such as: the multiplicity of civilizations and the establishment of markets such as the” okkaz” market.

2.1. THE SIGNIFICANCE OF ARABIC LANGUAGE

Arabic language is very important for all Muslims around the world. It is the language of the Holy Quran where the Holy Quran revealed in terms of meanings, structures, and very eloquent sentences. Arabic language contains many metaphors, and eloquent linguistic styles, which increased the importance of Arabic language. It is becoming the only timeless language in the world, which is the language of prayer and it is quite essential to engage in many of the Islamic worships. Arabic language is considered a major ritual language in several Christian churches in the Arab world.

The spread of Islam in many countries increases the importance of Arabic language, as it became the language of politics, science, and literature for some centuries, where the Arab authors wrote their writings in a distinctive way than others, as their writings talk about more than one scientific specialization and this shows the genius of the Arabic language.

In addition, Arabic language has a direct and indirect effect on many other languages in the Islamic world such as the Turkish, Persian, and many other Muslim countries.

Figure 1 illustrates the number of spoken languages in the world in 2018 as the Arabic language occupies the fourth level by 315 million, after Chinese which is 1299, Spanish 442, and English 378 [12].

Figure 1: Most spoken languages in world

2.2. CHARACTERISTICS OF ARABIC LANGUAGE

Arabic Language has many characteristics such as:

- Systematic: Contains a set of subsystems of sound, morphology, grammar, and semantics that guide the use of language.
- Symbolic: A set of signals approved by the speakers to infer things.
- Context: Context defines the meaning of the language and the meaning of words.
- Voice: The Origin in the language is the audio side and not the text.
- Customary: that is, people are the ones who agree on meanings and rules.
- Humanity: a phenomenon linked to humans.
- Communication: it must convey meaning and achieve effective communication between people.
- Cultural: Each language expresses a specific culture agreed upon by its people and passed on from generation to generation.

2.3. ARABIC LANGUAGE AND INTERNET

The internet is the main gate of communication between people relating with each other and to exchange information. Arabic language involves linguistics, grammar, semantics, rhymes, reading, and writing laws, letters, Arabic poetry, and speeches. Each of those types has different rules as standards to make it professional. Arabic language has a global audience to read and to learn.

Figure 2 : Percentage of websites content using various languages (Feb 2019)

Figure 2 shows the percentage of websites content using various languages[12]. The first language is English language with 54%, Russian is 6%, German is 5.9%, Spanish is 5%, French is 4%, Japanese is 3.4%, Portuguese is 2.9, Italian is 2.3, Persian is 2%, Polish is 1.7 and the last is Chinese with 1.7% as well as the other languages including Arabic language which is 11%. This means Arabic language is not between the top 11 languages in this side.

Table 1: Most spoken languages and websites content

Language	Chinese	Spanish	English	Arabic	Portuguese	Russian	Japanese
Number (Millions)	1299	442	378	315	223	154	128
websites content %	1.7%	5%	54%	0.6%	2.9%	6%	3.4%

Table 1 shows that English language has a good number of which it is spoken which stands at 378 million and the highest percentage of websites content is 54%. While some languages like Spanish, Portuguese, Russian, and Japanese have a good number of people who speak the language and they have relative ratios of websites content. Considering the number of people that speak Arabic which is 315 million, then websites content with Arabic content is 0.6%. Therefore, Arabic language has a good number of people who speak it but very little percentage of website content.

2.4. ARABIC LANGUAGES LETTERS

The Arabic language letters which is made up of 28 letters, starts with (ā, ĩ) and ends with (yā, ı). Table 2 shows seven columns to describe the Arabic letters sound in Arabic language using English language. Arabic language letters have different shapes according to the location in the word, which means there are three shapes that are included at the beginning of the word, in the middle of the word, and at the end of the word; those shapes do not have an effect on the sound of letters.

Table 2: Arabic Language Letters [13]

Sound	Isolated letter	Name in English	Name in Arabic	The letter at the beginning of the word	The letter in the middle of the word	The letter at the end of the word
ā	أ	alif	الألف	ا	ا	ا
b	ب	baa'	الباء	-□	ب	ب
t	ت	tā'	التاء	-[ت	ت
th	ث	thā'	الثاء	-[ث	ث
dj	ج	jīm	الجيم	-□	ج	ج
H	ح	hā'	الحاء	-□	ح	ح
kh	خ	khā'	الخاء	-□	خ	خ
d	د	dāl	الدال	د	د	د
dh	ذ	dhāl	الذال	ذ	ذ	ذ
r	ر	rā'	الراء	ر	ر	ر
z	ز	zāy	الزاي	ز	ز	ز
s	س	sīn	السين	-□	س	س
sh	ش	shīn	الشين	-□	ش	ش
S	ص	ṣād	الصاد	-□	ص	ص
D	ض	ḍād	الضاد	-□	ض	ض
T	ط	ṭā'	الطاء	ط	ط	ط
Z	ظ	ẓā'	الظاء	ظ	ظ	ظ

c	ع	'ayn	العين	ع	ع	ع
gh	غ	ghayn	الغين	غ	غ	غ
f	ف	fā'	الفاء	ف	ف	ف
q	ق	qāf	القاف	ق	ق	ق
k	ك	kāf	الكاف	ك	ك	ك
l	ل	lām	اللام	ل	ل	ل
m	م	mīm	الميم	ـمـ	م	م
n	ن	nūn	النون	ـنـ	ن	ن
h	هـ	hā'	الهاء	هـ	هـ	هـ
W	و	wāw	الواو	و	و	و
Y	ي	yā'	الياء	يـ	يـ	يـ

Arabic language letters scripts are used in many other languages in different countries. The languages are Malaysian Language (Jawi) which is still used in some reading and writing text, although the English letter is most spreadin formal using. Likewise,Iranian languages (Persian) uses the Arabic letters as a formal script [18], the Ottoman Turkish, Urdu [16], Azerbaijani, Sindhi, Punjabi, Kashmiri, Uyghur.

3. LANGUAGE LEARNING WEBSITES

In [1],various factors should be taken into consideration through website design. Those criteria make the websites standard and useful.

Figure 3: Primary criteria for Websites

Figure 3 shows the primary criteria of a professional website which include the purpose of a website to be clear and specific through its objectives and the content. Accuracy in presenting the content. Currently should have a good quality content and should be updated regularly. Authority who have the responsibility to manage the website. Loading speed in all website contents and files if there are as well as the website should be useful which means the content and activities should be beneficial. Organization or Navigation relates to a good interface and usability. Reliability means that the website should be active in all links and valid at the same time without bugs.

Figure 4: Secondary criteria for Websites

Figure 4 shows the secondary criteria for websites which include Authenticity meaning the content of the website as originally from the author. Interactivity, communication or feedback, which means there should be the interaction between the user and website management when the need arises. Multimedia that includes text, videos, graphics, images, and sounds. Finally, integration with other content or materials that are related to each other such as curriculum plans.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this section, we will discuss the research methodology that was followed to conduct the study. There are two main kinds which include the quantitative and qualitative. The quantitative is based on statistical methods and mathematical analyses, while qualitative is objective in nature because it used the numbers in analyses, which is accurate rather than data interpretation or description. In this study, both quantitative and qualitative methods are used, which is based on data gathering and analyses. Qualitative method is used to gain a deeper understanding of the data which cannot be represented in quantitative method [14] [15]. The quantitative method used the statistics to distinguish between the Arabic language and other languages in two parts which are represented in most spoken languages in the world (Figure 1) and the percentage of websites content using various languages on Feb 2019 (Figure 2).

5. REVIEW OF ARTICLES

Arabic language learning is important for people as a second language as (national language) in some countries such as Iran, Mali, Niger, Senegal, and Turkey. As well as important for Muslims around the world because they need to learn the basics of Islam and perform Islamic duties which requires Arabic language

Table 3: Literature review of Arabic language learning

Articles	Advantages / pros	Disadvantages /cons
[1]	Evaluate Arabic language learning websites. So that, they proposed an evaluation model, based on a set of criteria in language skills includes reading, listening, writing, speaking, and web site criteria.	The methodology not clear because number of websites not mentioned. The website titles and URL not mentioned
[2]	This paper studied a Learning management System (LMS). to design of interactive learning activities and proposed a theoretical framework of Arabic learning that include (interaction tools, activities and students)	It is theoretical framework only, no real result available, the system and software not available.
[4]	It is a EZ-Arabic software to lean Arabic language for primary schools in Malaysia. It is tested by users and mentioned some of suggestions to improve the application. Such as interface, videos, content, and more	It only study for application to learning Arabic language, it is for primary schools (children).
[7]	This study focus in Arabic learning through the games. They mention that clearly in the study. The main purpose is to investigate the effect of game level on learners	It is limited for one place in single center, it is concentrate on games and its effects more than Arabic language learning
[8]	It is enhancement for article in [7]. It focus on learning vocabulary of Arabic language using Web-based	It is related to games more than Arabic language learning. it is vocabulary of Arabic language only .
[20]	They discussed Arabic learning through the interaction between the art works as a integral of culture and Arabic learning,	They focused on art works from one artist Ali Omar Ermes

Table 3 shows the articles that are based on Arabic language learning websites and computer-based system, of which some articles such as [1] are used to evaluate Arabic language learning websites. In [2], proposed framework. In [4], it used studied computer-based system for the primary school. While [7] [8] used games through learning.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the aforementioned content analysis for some research papers related to Arabic language teaching and learning. This research paper concluded that there is still a huge shortage in the scientific articles that study the Arabic language learning through websites which requires taking a decision from the Arab universities and institutions so as to enhance and increase the Arabic website content and articles of Arabic language in the global journals, for example, to increase these websites and enrich their scientific content to increase the opportunities of its spread and education. There is also a clear lack of research related to this subject as the research papers that are directly related to this subject are still few and need more attention from Arab researchers and Arab institutions. In future work, we will study the contents of the website which used Arabic language to make a guide on how to improve the website's contents.

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